

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm Three

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>A Psalm of David, when he fled from Absalom his son.</p> <p>¹ O LORD, how my adversaries have increased! Many are rising up against me.</p> <p>² Many are saying of my soul, "There is no deliverance for him in God." Selah.</p> <p>³ But You, O LORD, are a shield about me, my glory, and the One who lifts my head.</p> <p>⁴ I was crying to the LORD with my voice, and He answered me from His holy mountain. Selah.</p> <p>⁵ I lay down and slept; I awoke, for the LORD sustains me.</p> <p>⁶ I will not be afraid of ten thousands of people who have set themselves against me round about.</p> <p>⁷ Arise, O LORD; save me, O my God! For You have smitten all my enemies on the cheek; You have shattered the teeth of the wicked.</p> <p>⁸ Salvation belongs to the LORD; Your blessing <i>be</i> upon Your people! Selah.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד בְּבָרְחוֹ מִפְּנֵי אֲבֻשָׁלוֹם בְּנוֹ :² יְהוָה מִה־רַבּוֹ צָרִי רַבִּים קָמִים עָלַי :³ רַבִּים אֹמְרִים לְנַפְשִׁי אֵין יִשׁוּעָתָה לּוֹ בְּאֱלֹהִים סֵלָה :⁴ וְאַתָּה יְהוָה מִגֵּן בְּעַדִּי כְבוֹדִי וּמְרִים רֹאשִׁי :⁵ קוֹלִי אֶל־יְהוָה אֶקְרָא וַיַּעֲנֵנִי מִהַר קֹדֶשׁוֹ סֵלָה :⁶ אֲנִי שָׁכַבְתִּי וְאִישָׁנָה הִקְיָצוּתִי כִּי יְהוָה יִסְמְכֵנִי :⁷ לֹא־אִירָא מִרַבְּבוֹת עַם אֲנִשְׁר סָבִיב שָׁתוּ עָלַי :⁸ קוֹמָה יְהוָה הוֹשִׁיעֵנִי אֶלְהִי כִּי־הִכִּיתָ אֶת־כָּל־אֹיְבֵי לִחְיִי שְׁנֵי רָשָׁעִים שִׁבַּרְתָּ :⁹ לִיהוָה הִישׁוּעָה עַל־עַמֶּךָ בְּרַכְתֶּךָ סֵלָה :</p>

Targum

¹ A psalm of David, when he fled from the presence of Absalom his son. ² O LORD, how many are my oppressors, many who arise against me. ³ Many say to my soul, "There is no redemption for him in God forever." ⁴ But you, O LORD, are a shield over me, my glory and the one who raises my head. ⁵ I pray [with] my voice in the presence of the LORD; he will accept my prayer from the mount of his sanctuary forever. ⁶ I lay down, and I slept; I awoke, because the LORD sustains me. ⁷ I will not be afraid of the strife of people who have gathered against me all around. ⁸ Arise, O LORD, redeem me, O my God; for you have struck all my enemies on their cheek, you have broken the teeth of the wicked. ⁹ Redemption is from the presence of the LORD; your blessings are to your people forever.

Interlinear

O	Lord יהוה yhwh	how מָה mah	my	adversaries צָר tzar	have	increased רָבַב ravav			
	Many רַב rav	are	rising קוּם qum	up	against עַל al	me			
Psa. 3:2 Lex Lex Trl	Many רַב rav	are	saying אָמַר amar	of	my	soul נֶפֶשׁ nefesh			
	There אֵין ayin	is	no אֵין ayin	deliverance יְשׁוּעָה yeshu'ah	for	him	in		
	God אֱלֹהִים elohim	Selah סֵלָה selah							
Psa. 3:3 Lex Lex Trl	But	You	O	Lord יהוה yhwh	are	a	shield מָגֵן magen		
	about בְּעַד ba'ad	me	My	glory כְּבוֹד kavod	and	the	One	who	lifts רוּם rum
	head רֹאשׁ ro'sh								my
Psa. 3:4 Lex Lex Trl	I	was	crying קָרָא qara'	to	the	Lord יהוה yhwh	with	my	voice קוֹל qol

And He answered me from His holy mountain
עָנָה קֹדֶשׁ הַר
anah qodesh har

Selah
סֵלָה
selah

Psa. 3:5 I lay down and slept
Lex שָׁכַב שָׁכַב יָשָׁן
Lex Trl shakhav shakhav yashen

I awoke for the Lord sustains me
קִיץ יְהוָה סָמַךְ
qitz yhwh samakh

Psa. 3:6 I will not be afraid of ten thousands of people
Lex יָרֵא רַבָּבָה רַבָּבָה עַם
Lex Trl yare' revavah revavah am

Who have set themselves against me round
אֲשֶׁר שִׁיתָ עָלַי סָבִיב
asher shit al saviv

about
סָבִיב
saviv

Psa. 3:7 Arise O Lord
Lex קוּם יְהוָה
Lex Trl qum yhwh

save me O my God For You have
יָשָׁעַנִי אֱלֹהִים
yasha' elohim

smitten all my enemies on the cheek You
נָכַחַת כָּל אֹיְבֵי לְחֵי
nakhah kol ayav lechi

have shattered the teeth of the wicked

Superscript

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
A Psalm of David, when he fled from Absalom his son.	מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד בְּבָרְחוֹ מִפְּנֵי אֲבִשָׁלוֹם בְּנוֹ׃

Superscript Analysis

Psalm One and two tell the story of the glory of King David. It is interesting that when the book of Psalms was put together, this Psalm became Psalm three. This Psalm talks about the punishment from Gevurah concerning David's immoral affair with Bathsheba. When word got out about David's sin, his firstborn son Absalom decided to lead a revolt to remove David from the throne of Israel. There were plenty of David haters who went along with Absalom. David's sin caused him to lose the gains that he had made on the Ladder of Ascent. David backslid because his Nefesh was strong enough that it caused him to want what the material world offered. The Nefesh is sometimes difficult to control. Psalm three demonstrates that humans are not perfect – there is no superhuman perfection.

Whenever the name David occurs before the phrase "a song," divine inspiration comes first. When "a song" is before the name of "David," it means that David elevated himself to the level of holy exultation because of his Psalm.

In this Psalm, David put himself in front of the LORD for judgment. He appealed to the Sefirot Gevurah for judgment, punishment, and forgiveness of his sin.

Superscript Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A song of David as he fled from his son Absalom. David placed himself before Gevurah for judgment and viewed Absalom's revolt as a part of his punishment.

Verse One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
1 O LORD, how my adversaries have increased! Many are rising up against me.	יְהוָה מִה־רַבּוֹ צָרָי רַבִּים קָמִים עָלַי :

Verse Analysis

The Absalom revolt was a part of David's atonement for his double sin. The first sin was adultery. The second sin was premeditated murder. The oppressors are the people who were against David and joined Absalom during the revolt.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

LORD, how many of my political enemies have joined Absalom in his revolt.

Verse Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
² Many are saying of my soul, "There is no deliverance for him in God." Selah.	רְבִיִּים אֹמְרִים לְנַפְשִׁי אֵין יְשׁוּעָתָה לֹא בִּאלֹהִים סֶלָה :

Verse Analysis

The soul is considered the Nefesh, Ruach, and Neshamah. David turned to the Sefirah Gevurah for help. David knew that judgment had to come to him. By pleading to Gevurah, he received judgment and punishment immediately. He did hope that Chesed would be able to shine mercy on him. If not, he was ready to accept Gevurah's punishment for his sins.

The people of Israel believed that David would not receive help from the LORD. But David's appeal to Gevurah did bring him forgiveness. The Sefirah Gevurah can give judgment while punishing him.

Selah, at the end of a verse, is there to tell the reader that he/she should pause and meditate on the verse.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The people of Israel did not believe that the Sefirah Gevurah would forgive David because David's two sins required the death punishment, according to the Torah.

Verse Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
³ But You, O LORD, are a shield about me, my glory, and the One who lifts my head.	רְבִים אֲמָרִים לְנַפְשִׁי אֵין יְשׁוּעָתָה לֹא בֵּאלֹהִים סִלָּה :

Verse Analysis

David believed that the Sefirah Chesed would shine love and mercy on him even during a time of Gevurah's judgment. David's chastisement was intended to guide him to a better future. It also brought him back to understanding that he needed to control the urges of his Nefesh. There is the hope of forgiveness for all sinners.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Chesed was with David even after his sin, and he knew that he would be restored in both the material and the spiritual world. He would be allowed to reascend the Ladder of Ascent.

Verse Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁴ I was crying to the LORD with my voice, and He answered me from His holy mountain. Selah.</p>	<p>וְאַתָּה יְהוָה מִן־הַצִּיּוֹן וּמִרְיֵם רֵאשִׁי׃</p>

Verse Analysis

David believed that if the LORD heard his voice while weeping, then it will be the LORD whom he was calling.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD knows my cry for help before I say it because I cried on the holy mountain of Zion. (Pause and meditate on this verse.)

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
5 I lay down and slept; I awoke, for the LORD sustains me.	קוֹלִי אֶל־יְהוָה אֶקְרָא וַיַּעֲנֵנִי מִתֵּר קוֹדֵשׁוֹ סֵלָה :

Verse Analysis

אֲנִי שָׁכַבְתִּי (ani shachav'tea) – connotatively means "I take the assurance that the LORD has heard me." David was confident that the LORD would hear his prayers.

שָׁכַב (shacar) definitions:

1. lie down
 - a. prostrated
 - b. to sleep,
 - c. lie on
 - d. lie
 - e. lie, of lamb
2. lodge (for the night)
3. of sexual relations

David never panicked because he always felt the Shekinah was with him. The Shekinah led David on his way when he fled from Absalom. David placed his trust in the Shekinah to lead him to the green pastures.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

David was able to sleep through the night because he knew the Shekinah would protect him.

Verse Six

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
6 I will not be afraid of ten thousands of people who have set themselves against me round about.	אֲנִי שֹׁכְבֹתִי וְאֵינְשָׁנָה הַקְּיָצוֹתַי כִּי יִהְיֶה יְסָמְכֵנִי׃

Verse Analysis

רְבָבָה (r' vava) – means “multitude, myriad, ten thousand.” Generally, in David's day, anything over one thousand was considered a significant amount. Therefore, any number of over one thousand is a good translation. The Targum does not offer a number.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

David's confidence in the LORD was strong that he did not fear Absalom.

Verse Seven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁷ Arise, O LORD; save me, O my God! For You have smitten all my enemies on the cheek; You have shattered the teeth of the wicked.</p>	<p>קוֹמָה יְהוָה הוֹשִׁיעֵנִי אֱלֹהֵי כִי- הַכִּיתָ אֶת-כָּל-אֹיְבֵי לְחֵי שֹׁנֵי רְשָׁעִים שִׁבַּרְתָּ</p>

Verse Analysis

Gevurah pronounced judgment over David's foes before they revolted because David was the LORD's anointed. Gevruah was not going to allow an enemy of David to remove him from the throne. Therefore, it can be said that the enemy of David was an enemy of the LORD. David's foes violated the Torah by attacking him.

Materialistic people violate the Torah because they are either ignorant of the spiritual world or do not want to be a part of it. David's enemies wanted the material gains of overthrowing the standing government.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Rise LORD and save David because Gevurah already judges his enemies as wicked.

Verse Eight

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
Salvation belongs to the LORD; Your blessing <i>be</i> upon Your people! Selah.	לִיהְיֶה תְּשׁוּעָה עַל־עַמּוֹךָ בְּרַכְתֶּךָ סֵלָה :

Verse Analysis

This verse is the reflective recantation of the call to Gevurah over his enemies, which David mentioned in verse seven. David concluded the Psalm by saying that the experience with Absalom taught him a lesson about allowing the Nefesh to take control of his soul.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD granted victory to His people with His blessings through the Shekinah.
(Pause and meditate on this verse.)

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A song of David as he fled from his son Absalom. David placed himself before Gevurah for judgment and viewed Absalom's revolt as a part of his punishment.

¹ LORD, how many of my political enemies have joined Absalom in his revolt.

² The people of Israel did not believe that the Sefirah Gevurah would forgive David because David's two sins required the death punishment, according to the Torah.

³ Chesed was with David even after his sin, and he knew that he would be restored in both the material and the spiritual world. He would be allowed to reascend the Ladder of Ascent.

⁴ The LORD knows my cry for help before I say it because I cried on the holy mountain of Zion. (Pause and meditate on this verse.)

⁵ David was able to sleep through the night because he knew the Shekinah would protect him.

⁶ David's confidence in the LORD was strong that he did not fear Absalom.

⁷ Rise LORD and save David because Gevurah already judges his enemies as wicked.

⁸ The LORD granted victory to His people with His blessings through the Shekinah. (Pause and meditate on this verse.)

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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